

PARTICIPATION OF A ATTORNEY IN THE PROCESS OF EVIDENCE IN A CIVIL COURT: PROCEDURAL ACTIONS AND PROCEEDING DOCUMENTS

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Abstract. This thesis is dedicated to the discussion of lawyers' arguments in civil courts.

Keywords: court, lawyer, evidence, method, defense.

It is known that the topic "Participation of a lawyer in civil proceedings" is one of the most discussed and topical topics of the decade. A lot of scientific works have been written on this issue and a large number of judgments have been made. However, this topic does not lose its relevance due to the fact that the process of reforming the judicial system and the institution of advocacy does not stand still.

Currently, lawyers, being participants in legal proceedings, perform a number of publicly significant functions, in connection with which they are reasonably subject to increased qualification and moral and ethical requirements.

That is why the institution of the bar is in the constant sphere of attention of the state and society, and the combination of the public nature of the functions of the bar and the independence of the bar community is the basis of the relationship between the bar, society and the state.

The work is devoted to the status and role of lawyers in the process of proving in a civil court. Such studies are important for improving the institution of the legal profession and raising the status of lawyers in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The relevance of the dissertation topic was that the protection of a citizen, the protection of his rights, freedoms and legitimate interests, both in a broad and narrow sense, should be a priority for the activities of any state. The proclamation in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the right to protection and receiving qualified legal assistance as one of the foundations of a democratic society predetermines the need for the practical implementation of this right.

The main purpose of the work was a detailed study of the rights and tasks of a lawyer as a representative in civil proceedings; clarification of the powers of a lawyer in relation to specific areas of activity; familiarization with the scientific organization of the advocacy; consideration of the provisions of the law on the participation of a lawyer at the stages of initiating a case, preparing the case for trial.

The purpose of the work was specified in the formulation of the following tasks:

Conducting a study of the institution of representation in civil proceedings by considering the concept, essence and meaning of the institution of representation, determining the subject composition of representation;

Analysis of the legal foundations of the status of a lawyer - a representative in civil proceedings;

Consideration of the features of the activities of a lawyer in the process of proof in civil proceedings.

The dissertation helps to clarify the general issues of the organization of the legal profession, the status of a lawyer and advocacy; the principles of the civil procedure that determine the status of a lawyer (freedom of evidence assessment, observance and protection of human and civil rights and freedoms in civil proceedings, etc.); time and registration of the beginning and end of participation in the civil process of a lawyer as a representative; the rights and obligations of a lawyer with his participation in a civil process at the stage of initiating a case, the stage of preparing a case for trial and at the stage of proof.

A certain obstacle in the work of a lawyer in civil cases is the lack of proper legislative regulation on a number of significant issues. Some questions are not reflected, others require fundamental clarifications. The normal functioning of the judicial system in general, and the work of a lawyer in particular, depends on the resolution of already urgent problems and the timely legislative response to issues that arise in practice.

The theoretical and practical significance of the study was due to the fact that the scientific results obtained as a result of the master's work, the experience of foreign countries, conclusions and suggestions can be used in the process of improving advocacy and the legal status of lawyers.

References:

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